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***Distimake quinquefolius* (Convolvulaceae): An addition to the flora of Banaskantha, North Gujarat**

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Abstract- *Distimake quinquefolius* (L.) A.R.Simoes & Staples, a new species from the Banaskantha district of Gujarat, India. Detailed descriptions along with colored photographs, distribution, ecological notes are provided for its easy identification

Key words: Banaskantha, North Gujarat, *Distimake quinquefolius*

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Distimake* (Convolvulaceae) is represented by 100 species, and distributed in the tropical regions of the world.¹ In India, over 15 species are reported.² Therefore, *Distimake quinquefolius* was recorded from Gujarat state.³⁻⁵ During field work the author collected unknown specimen from Vashi village of Danta taluka, in Banaskantha district, during December, 2023. On critical study of these specimens using relevant taxonomic literatures³, online e-floras (e-floraofindia) and illustrations, exploration of floristic literatures^{4,6-12} revealed that this species has not been recorded from whole Banaskantha till date. Therefore, *Distimake quinquefolius* (L.) A.R.Simoes & Staples, was reported by us for the first time, for addition in the flora of the state of Gujarat. A detailed taxonomic description and photographs of diagnostic characters of the species is provided here which was recorded from Banaskantha during December 2023, to facilitate its easy field identification.

MATERIAL & METHODS

Morphological description and ecological information presented here are based on field observations and materials collected during fieldwork of the Vashi village, Banaskantha in the period of December, 2023. Species identification was confirmed by comparison with the pertinent literatures.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Distimake quinquefolius (L.) A.R.Simoes & Staples, is a large perennial twinning herb. Stem slender, cylindrical, hirsute, leaves compound, digitate, petiolate, petiole 2-2.5cm, leaflets 3-5 foliolate, obovate to narrow lanceolate, central leaflets about 0.8- 5.5 cm long, lateral leaflet 0.5-2 cm, margin entire or dentate, cuneate at base, apex acuminate. Flowers white or creamy, solitary or in 3-5 flowered, axillary cyme, peduncle long 3.5-6 cm, pedicillate, pedicel 0.5 -1.2cm long, bracts minute, calyx 5, persistent, sepals 4-6mm cm long, unequal, the two outer smaller, mucronate at apex, 6-7 mm long, the inner 3.5- 6.5 mm long. Corolla campanulate, white or creamy white or pale yellow, 2-2.5 cm long. Stamens 5, included, epipetalous, anther basifixed, hastate. Carpels 2, ovary

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superior, axile placentation, stigma bilobed, globose. Capsule subglobose or obovoids, 6-8 mm in diameter, opening irregularly by 4 valves, trigonous, straw coloured, pubescent. Seeds 4, ovoid greyish black, 2 -5 mm.

Flowering & Fruiting: August-January.

Habitat: A common twiner along hedges on the moist evergreen and mixed deciduous forests.

Locality: Banaskantha, North Gujarat, India.

Figure 1 - *Distimake quinquefolius* (L.) A.R.Simoes & Staples.

A to C- Flower, D-Twing, E and F- Leaves, G- Androecium, H- Gynoecium, I and J- Fruit

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